

At a glance

12

Partners

7

Countries

3

Years

3.97M€

EU funding

Meet our partners

Project coordinated by

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ASTERISK

SEAWATER ELECTROLYSIS

Transforming seawater
into **green hydrogen**

Clean Hydrogen
Partnership

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Find us at
www.asteriskproject.eu

Cathode

This is our **electrolyser**, a device that splits water into its components, hydrogen and oxygen.

Through a process called **electrolysis**, an electric current breaks water molecules down. Opposing chemical reactions take place at the electrodes, known as the cathode and anode, making this possible.

At the **cathode** (the negative electrode), electrons trigger a reduction reaction to create hydrogen and hydroxyl ions— ready to travel to the other side through the membrane.

As a result of this process, we obtain **hydrogen** at the cathode.

Membrane

Every electrolyser needs a **membrane** that allows the selective movement of ions —electrically charged particles— from the cathode to the anode. Although membranes usually contain certain polluting materials, such as the so-called 'forever chemicals', at ASTERISK seek substituting PFAS with non-toxic alternatives.

Anode

At the **anode** (the positive electrode), hydroxyl ions are oxidised into oxygen and water. The electrons generated go back into the electrical circuit.

To speed up the chemical reactions that take place inside the cathode and the anode, we use **catalysts**. Ours come with a twist— instead of making them with scarce materials like platinum, we look for more abundant alternatives, such as iron or nickel.

As a result of this process, we obtain **oxygen** at the anode.

Water, a precious resource

Usually, the production of hydrogen through electrolysis uses fresh water. However, at ASTERISK we want to preserve this scarce resource, key for more important uses such as agriculture, farming, and human consumption.

Agriculture

Human consumption

Farming

Therefore, our project uses **seawater** as the source for hydrogen. This is a major technological challenge, as seawater contains impurities like microplastics or microorganisms that complicate electrolysis. In addition, sea salt corrodes our expensive components!

Democratising access to energy

As seawater is a natural and abundant resource, our electrolyser will work in **remote locations**, such as islands and off-shore. In this way, we guarantee access to energy, a fundamental aspect of any democratic society.

Scan to watch our animation, starring me!"

Circularity, a key aspect

For us, the key to our project is not what we do, but how we do it. At ASTERISK we make our systems as circular as possible. To do this, we will recover industrially important salts from the seawater, **valorising** the brine residues and returning water to the sea much cleaner!

12

Mg

Magnesium

20

Ca

Calcium

38

Sr

Strontium

3

Li

Lithium